

COMPETENCES OF EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM MANAGERS PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: Teaching using interactive methods, independent acquisition of all-round scientific theoretical knowledge, formation of knowledge and skills and formation of scientific worldviews based on this, formation of teacher-student cooperation

Keywords: manager, competence, special competence, social competence, professional competence, education, integrated.

The President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev at the extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers dedicated to the main results of socio-economic development in 2016 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2017 "Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal In his report entitled "responsibility - should be the daily rule of every leader's activity", teaching young people special subjects, as well as the history of our country and world civilization, foreign languages, and modern computer programs in a high-quality and full volume. noting that the issues of teaching have not yet been resolved, that the professional training of pedagogues and teaching staff is in some cases insufficient, therefore, creating a favorable environment for the development of teaching, learning, spiritual and moral education processes paid great attention to the necessity.

Also, among the most urgent tasks of today, there is an important way to further develop the scientific research activities carried out in the structures of the Academy of Sciences and higher education institutions in a coherent manner, to strengthen the material and technical base of scientific research institutions at the level of advanced foreign centers. the foundation of our activities in these areas is the high level of professional competence of the management staff at all levels, readiness for an innovative approach to the tasks in their field.

Competence often refers to the knowledge and experiences manifested in a person's general ability to operate and his professional training.

based integrated qualities are implied. So, the concepts of competence and competence are broader than the concepts of knowledge, competence and skills,

because they include qualities such as the orientation of the person, the ability to feel problems, the ability to show thoroughness, and the ability to have flexible thinking. Competence (lat. sompeto - I am achieving, I am worthy, I am worthy) means knowledge, experience in one or another field, the dictionary meaning in Uzbek is "well-versed", "having experience". means names. Therefore, a person who is competent in a certain field

is considered to have the appropriate knowledge and ability to think reasonably about this field and to carry out effective activities in it. According to many foreign experts, interest in the competency approach and competency assessment is growing worldwide, and this innovative process has become an important factor in ensuring the quality of higher education.

Mirziyoev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rules of every leader's activity. "Uzbekistan", 2017. Soares L. A 'Disruptive' Look at Competency-Based Education. How the Innovative Use of Technology Will Transform the College Experience. 2012, 12 p.4 Competence is an appropriate type of thinking, which requires a system of concepts and understanding, the ability to perform practical activities, to quickly solve emerging problems and tasks. A.V. Khutorskoy defined competence as a set of interrelated qualities of a person (knowledge, skills, studies, methods of activity) given for the necessary qualitative productivity activity in relation to subjects and processes within a certain scope. A.K. Markova states that competence is an individual description or indicator of the level of compliance with the requirements of the profession. The emergence of the competent approach, which is a new research direction in education, and the spread of the concepts of "competence" and "competence" in foreign pedagogical and methodical sources began in the USA in the late 1960s and early 1970s, and in higher education institutions It has penetrated widely into the theory and practice of professional training of students.

Nowadays, it is no coincidence that the level of scientific research competencies of any specialist, especially the leading staff in the educational system, directly affects the quality and efficiency of management. Because a modern specialist, in addition to having general methodological and methodological knowledge of his field, should be able to effectively use innovative methods in his work, analyze the problem, work with a large amount of information, draw reasonable and correct conclusions. such skills should be continuously and systematically developed. The concept of competence is related to solving complex practical problems that require not only specific knowledge and skills, but also a specific strategy, appropriate emotions and attitudes, as well as the presence of a mechanism for controlling the entire system. The strategic task of education is the preparation of a competent specialist who can act effectively outside of educational situations and solve exemplary and problematic issues that arise in his professional activity. In the conditions of the transition to the model of competent training, the identification of teaching technologies that use a competent approach in higher schools will have a special relevance.

N.A. Muslimov distinguishes several types of professional competences, which show a person's maturity in professional activity:

Special competence - mastering one's professional activity at a sufficiently high level, being able to plan the next professional activity.

Social competence - mastering joint professional activity, cooperation,

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